

Methodologies, Technologies and Tools Enabling e-Government

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The third edition of the International Conference on Methodologies, Technologies and Tools enabling e-Government (MeTTeG) received a large number of submissions from 15 different countries. The Program Committee responsible for the review process was comprised of a total of 24 members from Europe and the USA. The work of this group of highly qualified experts was outstanding and made it possible to gather high quality papers in different areas related to e-Government:

- Real use cases of services in the Public Administration field.
- Academic research works applied to fulfill the needs identified in the domain.
- Theoretical reviews of problems, limitations and roadmaps for eGovernment.
- Attempts and initiatives aimed at increasing interoperability in the Public Administration context.
- Studies on security issues in the eGovernment area.

This special issue of the Journal of Universal Computer Science gathers the best five papers of the conference, which have been additionally reviewed and extended after the conference.

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